

The Long Road to Recovery:
***An Investigation into the Health and Wellbeing of Older Adults in India who Survived Covid-19 and its
 Implications for Social Work Practice***

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Abstract

The pandemic has undoubtedly affected almost every aspect of life for people around the world. However, the most affected are older adults living in developing countries like India. In fact, the second wave of the pandemic in India, was the most devastating wave so far. Now that the worst appears to be over, there is a need to study the impact of the pandemic on the wellbeing of older adults recovering from the virus in the country. Hence, the aim of the present study is to examine the long term impact of covid 19 on older adults, its connection with wellbeing, and the role of social workers in their recovery. A total of 203 older adults from India took part in the study. The results show that majority of the respondents have poor wellbeing and have been more frequently plagued by chest pains, fatigue, and isolation, ever since they became infected. Moreover, respondents who are female, those with co-morbidities, and are suffering from other problems such as frequent chest pains, fatigue, and feelings of isolation, have lower levels of wellbeing. The implications of social work practice have also been discussed in the full paper.

Keywords: Recovery; Older adults; Wellbeing; Covid-19; Health; Aged

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Declaration of Interest

The authors report that there are no competing interests to declare.

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Abstract

The pandemic has undoubtedly affected almost every aspect of life for people around the world. However, the most affected are older adults living in developing countries like India. In fact, the second wave of the pandemic in India, was the most devastating wave so far. Now that the worst appears to be over, there is a need to study the impact of the pandemic on the wellbeing of older adults recovering from the virus in the country. Hence, the aim of the present study is to examine the long term impact of covid 19 on older adults, its connection with wellbeing, and the role of social workers in their recovery. A total of 203 older adults from India took part in the study. The results show that majority of the respondents have poor wellbeing and have been more frequently plagued by chest pains, fatigue, and isolation, ever since they became infected. Moreover, respondents who are female, those with co-morbidities, and are suffering from other problems such as frequent chest pains, fatigue, and feelings of isolation, have lower levels of wellbeing. The implications of social work practice have also been discussed in the full paper.

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Introduction

Around the world, along with an improvement in the life expectancy of people with chronic illnesses, there has been a decrease in the number of family caregivers for the aged (Tompkins et al., 2020) and this is particularly concerning for everyone living in the pandemic era. In the past two years, there has been a tremendous amount of research interest on the impact of the pandemic on older adults (Bonifas, 2021). This is because, since the beginning of the spread of covid-19 in December, 2019 (Casagrande et al., 2020), there has been a lot of suffering worldwide with a death toll of 5.8 million as of this moment (WHO, 2022) and it is older adults who have been classified as the most vulnerable. Apart from the massive death toll, the pandemic has inflicted unbearable pain and untold suffering among older adults, who disproportionately suffer the more serious complications caused by the virus (Nanda et al., 2020). The damage was extensive, particularly during the initial wave. For example, in the US, the fatality rate was over ninety per cent among those who were eighty years or above and who were on ventilator support (Powell et al., 2020). It was also predicted early on that the pandemic induced lockdowns would lead to increased social isolation and loneliness among older adults worldwide (Wu, 2020). Accordingly, in 2020 and 2021, several studies from different parts of the world reported this growing and worrying trend (Kotwal et al., 2021; Savage et al., 2021; van Tilburg et al., 2021). The impact of the virus was felt early on in India as well with almost a million infections by July, 2020 (Ghosh et al., 2020). By September, 2020, 62,288 people in India had already lost their lives due to covid-19 (Chatterjee, 2020). The outbreak became extremely serious for older adults as they are more at risk of facing death than the young (Bhatnagar et al., 2021). It was not just death, but also isolation and lack of mental health support in general that led to a significant amount of suffering among older adults during lockdown (Vahia & Shah, 2020). Another relevant fact regarding this issue is that those with co-morbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and cardiac diseases, were found to be at a greater risk of experiencing severe illness caused by the virus (Dalal et al., 2020). Since many of these co-morbidities are found more commonly among older adults, this increases the risk of mortality

among them (Shahid et al., 2020). Although there have been studies that have warned about the long term effects of the covid restriction measures on the mental health of older adults and the general population (Gorenko et al., 2021; Stolz et al., 2021), the gravity of the problem is yet to be fully understood since it is has only been two years since the World Health Organization first announced the emergence of the pandemic (Singh & Singh, 2020). There have also been reports of certain long term physical consequences of covid-19 such as fatigue (Lopez-Leon et al., 2021), chest pain and shortness of breath (Yelin et al., 2020), and possibly even the progression of cancer (Saini & Aneja, 2021). These issues require a closer examination, especially among older adults who have been previously infected by the virus and are still recovering from the long term problems being posed by the virus. Currently, in India, there is a temporary sense of relief with the third wave powered by the Omicron variant that was first identified in South Africa in November, 2021 (Viana et al., 2022) subsiding. However, there is a paucity of studies on the long term effects of covid-19 on both the physical health and mental wellbeing of older adults in India. The researchers felt that now that the third wave has weakened and sufficient time has passed since the first wave, it is now appropriate to examine the long term impact of the virus on the study population. It is also hoped that the study will not just highlight the long term consequences of the virus being faced by older adults in India, but will also be able to provide suitable suggestions and throw light on its implications for social work practice. With these two objectives in mind, the present study was undertaken.

Materials and Methods

Since the present study is primarily aimed at investigating the possible long term impact of covid-19 on the physical and mental health of older adults in an objective and generalizable manner, a quantitative research method has been adopted by the researchers (Guo, 2013). Moreover, the study is exploring several facets connected to physical and mental wellbeing, that could help identify those previously infected older adults who need the most support among others in the Indian context. Now that three waves of the pandemic have swept the country, a clearer picture

could emerge, possibly leading to novel findings that have hitherto remained hidden. Hence, the present study adheres to an exploratory research design (Mollick, 2014).

Theoretical Framework

The researchers have adopted the self-determination theory as the theoretical base for the present study (Deci & Ryan, 2012). According to this theory, individuals experience psychological growth and satisfaction when they experience autonomy, that is, being in control of their own lives; competence or being able to perform tasks effectively; and connection, that is, feeling connected with others. The researchers believe that those respondents who are bogged down by problems such as co-morbidities, fatigue, chest pain, isolation, and other long term physical and psychological effects of covid-19, will have a lower level of wellbeing as a result of not being able to fully regain their ability of self-determination, and might require greater support in their long journey to recovery.

Tools of Data Collection

A questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. The first part had questions relating to the background characteristics of the respondents. The second part had covid and recovery related questions. Questions/items under this section included the number of months it had been since the respondents first got infected, the number of times they have been infected with covid, and whether they were feeling more fatigued and isolated, or experiencing chest pain, more often than they were before they became infected. The responses for all these issues were measured on a five point likert scale with responses ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree (McCroskey, 1966). It was also enquired whether the respondents were suffering from co-morbidities such as diabetes, high blood pressure, cardiovascular problems, and cancer. The rationale behind each of these questions/items being included in the questionnaire was based on previous studies that indicated that various forms of co-morbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular diseases could increase the risk of infection to covid-19 (Ejaz et al., 2020), and that fatigue (Yelin et al., 2020) and chest pain (Becker, 2020), could be long term consequences of

being infected with covid-19. Apart from this, there were also reports of covid-19 restrictions causing increased isolation (Fisher et al., 2021) and disruptions in the delivery of cancer care services (Richards et al., 2020). The third part contained the five item wellbeing scale developed by the World Health Organization (Topp et al., 2015) with a higher score indicating better wellbeing. This tool was included as existing literature suggests that the pandemic could negatively impact the wellbeing of older adults (del Rio et al., 2020; Fisher et al., 2021). The cronbach alpha value of the tool was found to be 0.89, which suggests that the scale is reliable (Taber, 2018). A pre-test was carried out using three respondents who did not find any difficulty in comprehending any of the questions/items in the questionnaire. Hence, no changes were made to the questionnaire before final deployment. The typical respondent had to spend about ten minutes to respond to the questionnaire.

Data storage and analysis

The collected data which was stored in a password protected personal computer was analyzed using PSPP, a data analysis software (Yagnik, 2014). Apart from descriptive statistics, the researchers used Kruskal-Wallis test, which is a non-parametric alternative to One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), to discover the association between the selected independent variables and wellbeing. The researchers chose Kruskal-Wallis over ANOVA since the Kruskal-Wallis test is more appropriate and powerful while dealing with non-normal distributions as in the case of the present data-set (Hecke, 2012).

Study Participants

As a result of the stigma attached to covid-19 in India (Bagcchi, 2020), it is challenging to come across individuals who would openly admit that they were infected with covid-19. Hence, the researchers adopted snowball sampling (Handcock & Gile, 2011), with a target of securing 200+ responses by contacting old age homes and through social work professionals working with older adults. A total of 206 responses were collected of which three were incomplete and therefore discarded. Hence, the final sample consists of 203 responses (N = 203) from different parts of the country.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Generally, those who are 60 years and above are considered to be older adults or a part of the elderly population (Pilania et al., 2019). This is why only those respondents who were 60 years or above and were previously infected with covid-19 have been included in the present study. However, those who were still infected with the virus were excluded from the study as the study is focused on the long term recovery process of those older adults who have been infected with covid-19.

Ethical Considerations

Apart from securing written consent from the respondents, the researchers have adhered to the ethical principles laid out in Belmont Report (Zucker, 2007) and have secured ethical clearance from the institution.

Results

The results of the percentage analysis can be seen in table 1. One interesting finding, among others, is that majority or the single largest majority of the respondents agree or strongly agree with the statement that ever since they became infected with covid, they have been feeling more fatigued (57.1 per cent agree and 19.7 per cent strongly agree) and isolated (45.8. per cent agree; and 11.8 strongly agree) apart from increasing instances of chest pain as well (44.8 per cent agree and 13.3 per cent strongly agree). This set of findings are in line with the existing literature on the matter (Ejaz et al., 2020; Yelin et al., 2020) and are worrying trends that need to be acknowledged and addressed at the earliest. As far as the level of wellbeing is concerned, the fact that a significant number of the respondents either have average (41.9 per cent) or poor levels (32.5 per cent) of wellbeing, provides support to the idea that covid among older adults and wellbeing could be inter-linked. This is because, in general, it is believed that wellbeing has a U-shaped trajectory (Luhmann, 2017) with middle aged adults experiencing the lowest levels of wellbeing and then experiencing an improvement in old age. However, in the present study, a different picture has emerged which hints at the possible role of covid on the wellbeing of respondents.

Results of the Kruskal-Wallis Test

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test can be seen in table 2. Due to space constraints, only the results that turned out to be statistically significant have been presented.

Gender and Wellbeing

As far as the relationship between gender and wellbeing among older adults is concerned, the findings of the present study are similar to the one observed in another recent study (Kieny et al., 2021). A cross-tab analysis between gender and health issues shows that majority (77.8 per cent) of the respondents with three or more than three health issues, were women. In this scenario, being previously infected by covid might also be a contributing factor leading to an overall decreased level of wellbeing since there is some evidence of covid having a great impact on the health and wellbeing of older women in particular (VoPham et al., 2022).

Health issues at the time of being infected and Wellbeing

One possible explanation for those with cancer and cardio-vascular problems having the lowest mean rank of wellbeing compared to others is the disruptions in access to regular health checkups, especially for cancer sufferers (Mitra & Basu, 2020) and cardio-vascular patients in the country (Kaushik et al., 2020). Additionally, as highlighted previously, there is some scientific proof that covid could lead to the progression of cancer (Saini & Aneja, 2021) and this in turn could be adversely impacting the wellbeing of the respondents after being infected.

Fatigue after infection and wellbeing

The results support the existing literature on post covid fatigue (Wostyn, 2021) which appears to be adversely impacting the wellbeing of the respondents. Unfortunately, a lower wellbeing among older adults who have been previously infected with covid might be incorrectly dismissed as a symptom of co-morbidities (Wang & Kim, 2020), which majority of the respondents in the present study do suffer from.

Chest pains after infection and wellbeing

The increase in the frequency of chest pains since being infected with covid is negatively impacting the wellbeing of the respondents. This is explained by the point that physical co-morbidities/health issues have been known to lower subjective wellbeing among individuals (Wang & Kim, 2020). Furthermore, a Spearman's rank correlation analysis between the number of months that have passed since being infected with covid and the issue of chest pains indicates that there is a statistically significant and negative correlation between both ($r = -0.20$; $p = 0.004$) which means that with the increase in the number of months since being infected with covid, the respondents are less likely to experience frequent chest pains. This provides statistical strength to the fact that covid and issues like chest pain that are closely associated with the wellbeing of respondents, are indeed inter-related.

Isolation after infection and wellbeing

The link between isolation and wellbeing among older adults has been documented (Chappell & Badger, 1989) and as expected, the same has been observed in the present study. Moreover, a Spearman's rank correlation between the number of months since being infected with covid and isolation has revealed that there is a statistically significant negative correlation between both ($r = -0.7$; $p = 0.0151$). In other words, as the number of months since being infected increases, the feelings of isolation among the respondents decrease. There is some evidence to link covid related policies and isolation among older adults (Brooke & Jackson, 2020) and the fact that this is also closely associated with lower wellbeing is very clear.

Discussion and Implications for Social Work Practice

In general, the majority of the respondents do not have a good level of wellbeing. Moreover, being female was found to be associated with lower levels of wellbeing. Apart from the fact that majority of those with three or more co-morbidities were women, the other possible factor that could be leading to lower levels of wellbeing among female respondents compared to males is that women in India are also expected to shoulder household responsibilities (Parikh, 2018). Therefore, it is suggested that social work practitioners working in women's welfare organizations could

organize webinars and workshops to help older women to better negotiate household responsibilities with their male partners so that the burden of responsibilities is equally shared between both genders. As far as co-morbidities is concerned, the government, hospitals, and non-governmental organizations need to collaborate to reach out to those suffering from co-morbidities and in particular, those suffering from serious ailments such as cancer and cardiovascular problems. Now that the internet connectivity in the country has developed to certain extent, telemedicine and tele-counseling services can be offered to such individuals on a regular basis, especially during lockdown periods. Furthermore, medical social workers could help organize meditation camps for people with physical health issues as it is shown to have beneficial effects on Individuals (Monk-Turner, 2003). For those who are experiencing fatigue, there might be a need for them to re-evaluate their lifestyle and seek the advice of dietitians and wellbeing experts on how to manage the problem. In the case of those who are in old age homes, there is a need for social work professionals working there to identify those who have recently recovered from covid and provide them with additional care until their symptoms improve and they are back to normal. Those who are experiencing frequent chest pains also require periodic check ups to prevent their symptoms from worsening. In this context, medical social workers could conduct home visits for those covid affected older adult patients who have been discharged from the hospital. This will help monitor the problem and help them secure medical assistance in time if the symptoms worsen. With regard to isolation among older adults and its association with wellbeing, social workers could conduct case work intervention with family to help improve the familial bonds and prevent older adults from feeling left out. For respondents who are in an old age homes, it is the moral and professional responsibility of the management to reach out to family members of the respondents and encourage them to visit their older adult relative from time to time. Apart from this, old age homes could work together with hospitals and conduct laughter therapy and employ program media to help lighten the atmosphere and improve bonding among members. Currently, there is a need to promote gerontology in India and encourage more social workers to explore as well as specialize in it,

because with the improved healthcare facilities, the population of the aged is set to increase in the coming years and to cater to their special needs, social workers need to be aptly trained and specialized in it. Although India has traditionally stood for strong family ties and deep familial bonds, over the years, the trend of leaving behind aged parents and moving abroad has been seen. While moving away to seek better economic opportunities is understandable, it also has to be accepted that this is resulting in a family void and is generating a sense of isolation among older adults that is certainly exacerbated by covid as the results suggest. This brings us to the other major issue which is yet to be fully investigated but there is sufficient proof of its existence, that is, the stigma associated with being infected. Even if the individual fully recovers from the infection, they are seen and often excluded, especially in rural areas where the knowledge on the subject among many, is limited. Hence, social work students and professionals could plan and organize awareness campaigns in both urban and rural areas, but particularly in rural areas on how the virus spreads and that an individual after recovering from the infection can no longer transmit the virus. Only when the perspectives of individuals on the matter change, can one witness a societal change, a change which will help ensure a better level of wellbeing among older adults who have survived covid and are recovering from its long term impact.

Conclusion

It appears that problems such as chest pains, fatigue, and isolation, among older adults are possibly aggravated by the virus as seen from the results. Even more troubling is the fact that very few respondents actually had a decent level of wellbeing, which is contrary to the U shaped trajectory of wellbeing in general. Older women in particular seem to have a lower level of wellbeing compared to older men. The findings of the study support the self-determination theory since those with no co-morbidities and less intense levels of chest pains, fatigue, and isolation, (often worsened by covid 19) are having a higher score of wellbeing and are more in control of their lives. Apart from the possible social work interventions that have been suggested, there is a dire need for an attitudinal shift in the way older adults affected by covid are viewed in today's society.

Only when their special needs are rightfully acknowledged, their long road to recovery from covid 19 can be truly successful.

Limitations of this study

The researchers could have adopted a mixed methodology as it would have resulted in an even more rich set of insights into the problems faced by older adults in this context. Perhaps future studies of this nature could incorporate this suggestion.

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Table 1-Percentage Analysis (N =203)

Variables	N	Percentage	Mean (min) (max)
Age group (yrs)			
60-70	160	78.8	68.18 (60) (95)
71 and above	43	21.2	
Gender of the Respondents			
Male	78	38.4	
Female	125	61.6	
Religion			
Hindu	61	30.0	
Muslim	03	1.5	
Christian	132	65	
Other	07	3.4	
Number of months since being infected with covid			
0-6 months ago	133	65.5	6.56 (1) (25)
7-12 months ago	50	24.6	
More than 12 months ago	20	9.9	
Health issues at the time of being infected with covid			
High blood pressure	40	19.7	
Cardiovascular problems	12	5.9	
Diabetes	63	31.0	
Cancer	04	2.0	
Two of the four health issues	30	14.8	
Three or more health issues	09	4.4	
No health issues	45	22.2	
Number of times being infected with covid			
Once	185	91.1	
Twice or more	18	8.9	
Compared to before being infected with covid, I now feel more fatigued/tired			
Strongly disagree	06	3.0	
Disagree	20	9.9	
Neither agree nor disagree	21	10.3	
Agree	116	57.1	
Strongly agree	40	19.7	

Compared to before being infected with covid, I now frequently experience chest pain			
Strongly disagree	19	9.4	
Disagree	41	20.2	
Neither agree nor disagree	25	12.3	
Agree	91	44.8	
Strongly agree	27	13.3	
Ever since I tested positive for covid, I feel more isolated from others			
Strongly disagree	31	15.3	
Disagree	36	17.7	
Neither agree nor disagree	19	9.4	
Agree	93	45.8	
Strongly agree	24	11.8	
Level of Wellbeing			
Very poor	07	3.4	
Poor	66	32.5	
Average	85	41.9	12.72 (1) (25)
Good	24	11.8	
Very good	21	10.3	

Table 2- Kruskal Wallis Test-Wellbeing (N = 203)

Gender					
	N	Mean rank	χ^2	df	p value
Male	78	115.85	7.08	1	0.008**
Female	125	93.36			
Health issues at the time of being infected with covid					
High blood pressure	40	93.33	20.24	6	0.003**
Cardiovascular Problems	12	76.79			
Diabetes	63	91.63			
Cancer	4	76.13			
Two or more health issues	30	108.93			
Three or more health issues	9	79.78			
No health issues	45	133.08			
Compared to before being infected with covid, I now feel more fatigued/tired					
Strongly disagree	6	136.75	33.52	4	0.000***
Disagree	20	153.35			
Neither agree nor disagree	21	138.31			
Agree	116	91.13			
Strongly agree	40	83.56			
Compared to before being infected with covid, I now frequently experience chest pain					
Strongly disagree	19	161.13	45.01	4	0.000***
Disagree	41	133.18			
Neither agree nor disagree	25	96.94			
Agree	91	85.70			

Strongly agree	27	72.65			
Ever since I tested positive for covid, I feel more isolated from others					
Strongly agree	31	155.23	46.92	4	0.000***
Disagree	36	123.26			
Neither agree nor disagree	19	103.87			
Agree	93	84.51			
Strongly disagree	24	67.65			

*** Statistically significant at a very high level ($p < 0.001$)

** Statistically significant at a high level ($p < 0.01$)

